

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN TOURISM

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Abstract

Nowadays, the tourism sphere developing through the world and using social media tools and websites also increasing in tourism industry. This article explores the potential of social media marketing. The role of social media marketing in tourism main aim to enhance the travel experience which provides personalized recommendations, up-to-date information, how to reach historical places by showing place and some interactive elements that cater to the needs of travelers. The observation was explored in Uzbekistan, to analyze the role of social media among residents. To gain data, survey shared among students, journalists and employees and analyzed with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program. By utilizing social media marketing strategies, the media will captivate users, advertise local attractions, and promote a feel of community between tourists and locals. The study highlights how the synergy among social media marketing and smart tourism technology can contribute to sustainable tourism development in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Social media; Network; Sustainable tourism; Marketing; SPSS

INTRODUCTION

Social media has a significant impact as a communication tool, as a travel guide or just for observe some information. People around the world use social media to share information with other people and organizations. They started using platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok and LinkedIn to connect with friends and relatives and communicate their experiences through social media, photos, videos and text messages. As a result, fast development of social media have revolutionized the tourism industry. Currently, most of travelers heavily depend on digital apps to observe, discover, plan and enhance to journeys. This study explores the opportunities of creating a Smart Tourism App for Uzbekistan. The platform is conceived as an exhaustive guide for travelers, provide the navigator how to reach in destinations, provides important information for tradition, history and real-time updates. Additionally, the success of the platform depends not only on its features but also on effective marketing strategies. Through direct advertising, partnership with influencers, and user-generated content, networking can enhance the platform's visibility and foster meaningful communications with travelers. This study explores how

the incorporation of network marketing and smart tourism technology can promote Uzbekistan's tourism sector and contribute to sustainable improvement within the industry.

According to author Lempert (2006), most of the customers changing their view from traditional means for example, radio and newspapers to modern means of communication. They now prefer the product which owns information online available from websites through platforms rather than old version paper. The customers search the information about the products or services online with a help of social media.

Researchers Abbasi et al. (2023) stated that most tourism organizations use social media marketing to increase tourist arrivals and attract more visitors through networking. However, utilizing social media marketing presents challenges, such as selecting the right content type, design, or visually appealing destination to capture tourists' attention on their first encounter. This paper examines the direct and indirect variables related to social media marketing images and influencers. Data was collected from 307 participants and analyzed using PLS-SEM-based mediation analysis. As a result, the hypothesized relationships were confirmed, providing meaningful insights and practical implications for enhancing the effectiveness of social media marketing in the tourism industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nowadays, social media marketing have become important tools for increasing tourism sector. Based on recent researches, social media influences travelers' choice-making processes. Social media has already appeared to be a vital and friendly part of human's living processes, as 71% of individuals are utilizing it more in 2021 than before. The upsurge was significantly impacted by occurrences that took place over the last couple of years. Due to the implementation of social distancing guidelines and the rise of remote work, individuals have heavily relied on social media platforms to communicate, interact, and conduct transactions. Social media is now comparable to traditional advertising methods such as TV or radio advertisements and word-of-mouth when it comes to discovering information about brands. According to a survey, 33% of consumers have expressed their preference to acquaint themselves with brands through this particular method in the future. Increasingly, social media platforms have become the favored destination of people in every sphere for purchase, alter destinations to travel or for other services.

According to Kotler et al., (2017) positive reviews which are online provide potential clients with authentic imagination about organization and unique product or service. Customers have been using these reviews to decide whether to buy or never to buy. They can also be used as a tool which creates understanding in terms of the brand. Even if the reviews are bad, the manner in which the company decides to respond to them can also prove to be very crucial for their brand image. The authors Alghizawi et al., (2018) observes that a remarkable improvement in the world like electronic tools, mainly the social media networking which improve many sectors including tourism sphere also. This position leads to competition between touristic companies and to their offers for tourists. As a result few studies have analyzed the influence of networks on promoting tourism in Jordan. The main of this exploration is mainly focus to improve some platforms which specialized especially for tourists. In addition, it examines the main role of enhancing local revenue generated by the tourism sphere. This study mainly addressed the essential position of increasing the local platform which is convenient for tourists who travels through the Jordan.

The authors Nuenen & Scarles (2021) analyzed the importance of social media in tourism sector. The article examines the simultaneous processes of promoting knowledge, attentiveness and obligation that digital technology facilitates in the tourism industry. The observation shows that, digital platforms, content, reels, real-time updates about tourism can increase international tourist arrivals. On the other side, countries should create specific platform for tourists which is easy to use for tourists and it should include information about historical places and should navigate them to some interesting places this kind of apps become popular among tourists. As a result online marketing and online platforms can boost tourist arrivals because travelers can guide by themselves and it can help tourists to save their money.

Drawing on recent exploration and theoretical frameworks like Cheung et al., (2021) examines the impact of social media-based destination brand community (SMDBC) on tourists' feeling and the role of social media. Survey data analyzed subscribes of Japanese network pages from 551 Chinese social media users. Result shows that social media-based destination brand community significantly affect tourists' sense like a joy, surprise and love which can influence on tourists intentions to co-create value and visit. This article highlights the important role of social media-based destination brand

community with other marketing and branding efforts to better explain its role to improve business, services and sales.

(1 picture)

Well-known social media platforms which have been utilized by most organizations or businesses to focus their clients are Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Telegram and Twitter.

•Facebook

Facebook is a social networking site that allows you to easily connect and communicate with your family and friends online from everywhere. Facebook has more than 3 billion users

Once accepted, the two profiles will be linked and both users will be able to see everything the other person has posted. "Facebook users" can post almost anything to their "feed" at any time, a snapshot of what's happening in their social circle, and chat with other friends online.

•Instagram

Nearly 2 billion estimated active users on Instagram in 2024, it is also very well-liked. Businesses use a range of strategies, such as Instagram Live and Instagram Stories, to advertise products and offered services on the platform. Instagram is a platform which primarily emphasizes multimedia, to market their goods and services, businesses work with influencers.

•Twitter

Twitter is a free social network where users share short messages known as tweets. These tweets can contain text, video, photos or links. To access Twitter, users need an internet connection or a smartphone to use the Twitter.com app or website.

Data and Methodology

This research is conducted in Uzbekistan, to analyze importance of social media among citizens and improve network system in tourism sphere. Data were collected through structured surveys distributed to students, journalists and employees resulting in 105 completed responses. Data were explored in both methods in primary and in secondary data were used to conduct the research. The primary data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) program with a help of using “Descriptive analysis” to summarize main features of answers.

Methodology

$$\text{Social media marketing (SMM)} = \beta + \alpha \text{Age} + \alpha^1 \text{gender} + \alpha^2 \text{usage}_{sm} + \alpha^3 \text{travel_ins_app} + \alpha^4 \text{Online_booktrip} + \alpha^5 \text{Type_of_con} + \alpha^6 \text{Recommend_infl} + \alpha^7 \text{Comment_importance} + \alpha^8 \text{engaging_TBC} + \alpha^9 \text{share_travel_exp} + \alpha^{10} \text{share_travel_expe} + \alpha^{11} \text{Type_inadequately_TB} + \varepsilon$$

$\alpha, \alpha_1 \dots \alpha_6$ --- are the coefficient of the independent variables; These are the coefficients of the independent variables in a statistical or econometric model. Each coefficient represents the strength and direction of the relationship between an independent variable and the dependent variable.

ε – error term. This represents the unobserved factors or randomness that affect the dependent variable but are not included in the model. It accounts for variations not explained by the independent variables.

β – constant. This is the value of the dependent variable when all independent variables are zero. It represents the baseline level of the dependent variable in the absence of other influencing factors.

		Frequencies	Percentage
Gender	Male	50	47.6
	Female	55	52.4
Age	Under 18	8	7.6
	19-25	67	63.8
	26-30	17	16.2
	31+	13	12.4

(1 graph)

Demographic analysis of respondents is included for those who took part in the research, which helps to clearly understand the background of respondents, using descriptive analysis. The study analyzed the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Of the total 105 respondents, 50 were male and 55 were female. In terms of age distribution, 8 respondents (7.6 %) were under 18 and 67 individuals were between 19-25 respondents (63.8 %). Another group of people were between 26 and 30 with 17 respondents (16.2), 13 responders (12.4%) were older 31.

RESULT (Findings)

(2 graph)

The survey results show the distribution of variety types of social media content among age groups. The content types involve ads, influencer posts, photos, and video/reels.

The most predominant content type is video/ reels particularly between 19-25 age groups with 46. The second popular content type is photos (8) and ads (7) among 19-25 years old groups. In contrast, other age groups illustrate a balance especially under 18 years old and 31+ age groups indicator shows the same result photos (4), videos/reels (3) and ads (5) and 3 influencers post among 31+ age group. Lastly, between 26 and 30 age group video/reels (9) are dominant compare to photos (7).

Overall, videos/reels are the most dominant content type among most of the age groups, especially between 19 and 25 years old, while other content type shows little bit significant.

(3 graph)

The bar graph shows the difficulties faced in social media marketing based on gender (male and female). The difficulties involve attracting influencers, deciding content type, reducing travel cost and understanding multilingual content.

The biggest challenge is understanding multilingual content, among both gender males (24) compare to females (17). The second biggest challenge is reducing travel cost for both genders. In addition, deciding content type was more difficult among females 11 compare to males 8. The last one is attracting influencers also was little bit difficult among females 10 compared to males 7.

Overall, understanding multilingual content is the huge problem among genders, while attracting influencers is the least challenging aspect in both genders. It means that, if countries increase to use international languages it can improve tourist arrivals in different places with a help of social media marketing.

Which social media platforms do you use often for travel inspiration? (Qaysi platforma sizni ko'proq sayohat qilishga ilhomlantiradi?)

105 responses

(4 graph)

This bar chart illustrates that which social media platforms more popular in Uzbekistan based on respondents answer. The most dominant social platform is Instagram with 68.6 % compare to other platforms. The second popular app is Facebook with 17.1 % people chose this app.

In conclusion, if touristic organizations use Instagram to improve their sales to travelers and show more interesting places with a help of platform it can increase their profit.

Have you ever booked a trip based on content you saw on social media? (Siz ijtimoiy media kontentiga asoslanib sayohat bron qilganmisiz?)

105 responses

(5 graph)

This pie chart illustrates the percentage of respondents that ever booked a trip based on social media content. If observe carefully, the most responders gives positive respond 59 % of them because some individuals also want to try book a travel based on network advertisement. However, 40 % of people do not prefer to book travel based on social media advertisement. It means that, most

of the people can book a trip with a help of social media ads and organizations should improve their online ads to attract more people from network database.

How likely are you to share your travel experiences on social media? (Siz sayohat tajribangizni ijtimoiy mediada ulashishga qanchalik tayyorsiz?)

105 responses

(6 graph)

The pie chart gives information about how likely people can share their travel experience on social media platforms or network. The huge number of individuals very likely to share their travel experience during their travel 40% compare to 29.5% of people neutral about their sharing experience through network. Additionally, 19% of people do not prefer to show their picture or videos about their travel but 11.4% of travelers somewhat likely prefer to share. From that graph we can understand that, majority of people prefer to share their travel experience through social media to their friends or families. If most of the people share their travel in their accounts it can influence to other people also, because from their trip people can discover new places for them and it can motivate them to travel another countries and to explore new destinations like their friends.

How important are customers comments on social media when choosing a destination or service? Please rate! (Sayohat joyini tanlashda ijimoiy medi...ikr va izohlar siz uchun muhimi? Iltimos baholang!)

105 responses

(7 graph)

This survey result illustrates about how important are customers comments on social media when choosing destination or some kind of services from social media marketing. The data based on 105 responses from local people, and participants rated importance of scale from 1 to 5. The most of the respondents support that customers comment on network vitally important 47.6% (5). 24 respondents gave a rating of 4 if means 22.9%. Also, other respondents 29.2% put unimportant rate from 1 to 3.

The majority of people 70.5 % consider that social media comments play essential role when choosing destination to travel. Only 29.2% respondents find that comments unimportant for them to travel from one place to another places.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This article explores the determinants of the role of social media marketing in tourism sphere in Uzbekistan using traditional gravity models and panel data analyses of 105 residents. Data were collected with a help of google form survey taking opinions from local people and both primary and secondary data were gathered to conduct the research. The primary statistics were analyzed with a help of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) program applying "Descriptive analyses" through cross-tabulation to provide the percentage of variables. To improve the tourist arrivals in countries, companies can use three popular platform to their online advertisement these are Facebook, YouTube and Instagram which are the most of people prefer to use these app. Second, organizations should use more video-reels to increase their viewers number because survey shows that people prefer video-reels which are related to tourism sphere.

However, when people using social media they can face to some challenges, the huge difficulties are understanding multilingual content, that is why travel agencies or organization should use international language to their content. Additionally, reducing travel cost also difficult for most people, companies should give discounts for online booking travels. Online booking a trip also become popular day by day which travelers interested based on content from social media.

On the other side, organization should motivate people to share travel experience through social media, because it can help to promote number of travelers. In addition, customer comments on social media plays crucial role for travelers when choose a destination for travel. And companies should take a care for travelers during their travel and it can increase number of good comments which can help them to increase tourist arrivals.

In light of the study results, the following are recommended: social media marketing should provide updated and truth information for travelers, also it should in international language that everyone can understand easily without misunderstanding. The Ministry of Tourism should take a care for improve online booking which is easy for the most of people to book a trip and during online booking travel organizations should give discounts maybe 5 or 10%. To improve online ads government should provide some laws for tourism agencies which can improve tourist arrivals, for instance during video-reels organizations can show national culinary of Uzbekistan, historical places or natural beauty which can attract more people. During a travel, organizations should take an interview from travelers about their experience and can share it through social media which help them increase tourist arrivals. The Ministry of Tourism should do some conferences to improve social media marketing in tourism sphere with organizations, companies and tourism agencies.

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